

Contamination and Consciousness: A Triangulated Study on Librarians' Awareness, Attitudes, and Practices in Managing Microbial Risks

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ABSTRACT

Background: Microbial contamination of print materials threatens both library collections and human health. Yet little is known about how Nigerian university librarians perceive and manage these risks.

Methodology: A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining a descriptive survey, direct observation, and semi-structured interviews. Data were collected from 239 librarians proportionately sampled from six federal university libraries. Questionnaires measured awareness, attitudes, and practices; observations assessed environmental conditions; interviews with library heads explored policies, challenges, and support systems.

Findings/Results: Awareness was high (77.8–94.4%), though professional training exposure varied, with UniPort and UniAbuja reporting lower access. Attitudes were largely positive, particularly at BUK and ATBU, which also showed stronger compliance with preventive practices (>80%), compared to weaker engagement at UniPort and UniAbuja (<60%). Observations revealed inadequate ventilation, poor humidity control, and limited preservation guidelines. Interviews highlighted institutional gaps: funding shortages restricted preservation supplies and equipment; policy frameworks were often informal or absent; training opportunities were irregular; and environmental monitoring was weak.

Implications: The findings reveal a disconnect between librarians' individual awareness and institutional capacity, underscoring that sustainable contamination control requires structured support beyond personal initiative.

Conclusion: Nigerian university libraries demonstrate commendable awareness and attitudes but remain constrained by weak policies, funding limitations, and poor environmental management.

Recommendations: Strengthening preservation policies, ensuring dedicated funding, expanding professional training, and enforcing environmental monitoring are critical to safeguarding both collections and health.

Keywords: Microbial contamination, librarians, awareness, attitudes, preventive practices, academic libraries, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Microbial contamination in libraries poses dual risks: it accelerates the biodeterioration of print resources and endangers the health of staff and users through exposure to fungi and bacteria Muthalagu et al. (2025). Conditions such as dust, humidity, poor ventilation, and heavy human use heighten these risks, especially in developing countries where environmental control infrastructure is often limited (Sundas et al., 2024). While preservation discourse has largely emphasized physical and chemical factors, biological threats are increasingly prominent and demand equal attention.

Despite numerous studies on microbial identification in library environments Jung et al., 2019; Camargo-Caicedo et al., 2024; Hempel, et al., 2014 less focus has been placed on librarians themselves, whose awareness, attitudes, and practices (AAP) significantly influence risk management. As custodians of information resources, their perceptions and actions shape how effectively microbial threats are recognized and mitigated. This study, therefore, explores the AAP of librarians regarding microbial contamination in six federal university libraries in Nigeria, using a triangulated descriptive survey design. By connecting environmental concerns with human consciousness and professional practice, the study aims to generate evidence that can inform sustainable preservation strategies and health-conscious library management policies.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite increasing recognition of microbial contamination as a threat to both library collections and human health, preservation research in Nigerian university libraries has predominantly focused on environmental conditions and material deterioration, with limited consideration of librarians' awareness, attitudes, and practices. Prior studies have documented the role of poor ventilation, high humidity, dust, and acidic paper in accelerating the deterioration of resources (Bankole & Abioye, 2005; Ejiwoye & Abioye, 2015; Olatokun, 2008; Osunrinde & Adetunla, 2017; Tsegba et al., 2018). For instance, Olatokun (2008) reported that preservation activities were often limited to routine dusting and cleaning, with little institutional commitment to advanced conservation measures. Similarly, Ejiwoye and Abioye (2015) highlighted unfavourable relative humidity and biological agents as major contributors to deterioration in Southern Nigerian university libraries. Studies on non-print resources (Tsegba et al., 2018) and localized assessments of university collections (Bankole & Abioye, 2005) further show that scholarship has remained concentrated on environmental deterioration processes, while the human and institutional dimensions of microbial risk remain underexplored.

This gap is particularly critical given that librarians, as frontline custodians of collections, play a central role in implementing contamination control measures. Their perceptions, knowledge, and institutional support structures directly influence the effectiveness of preservation outcomes. However, little empirical evidence exists on how librarians in Nigerian university libraries understand and respond to microbial risks, or the systemic barriers that shape their practices. Addressing this gap is essential for developing holistic contamination control strategies that integrate human, institutional, and environmental factors. Accordingly, this study examines librarians' awareness, attitudes, and practices concerning microbial contamination, with the aim

of generating evidence to inform policy, professional training, and sustainable preservation strategies in Nigerian university libraries.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To ascertain whether librarians are aware of microbial contamination in federal university libraries of Nigeria.
2. To examine librarians' attitudes towards microbial contamination in the libraries studied.
3. To identify the practices adopted by librarians to prevent microbial contamination in the libraries studied.
4. To examine the environmental conditions of university libraries studied that may influence microbial contamination.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Microbial Contamination in Library Environments

Microorganisms are ubiquitous in indoor environments, shaping air quality and influencing both human health and the integrity of materials. Fungi and bacteria are particularly problematic in libraries, where organic substrates such as paper and adhesives create favorable conditions for colonization. Their growth is driven by ecological factors such as temperature, humidity, pH, and ventilation, with poorly controlled environments accelerating microbial diversity and proliferation. In Nigeria, where high humidity and infrastructural limitations are common, these risks are especially acute (Akor, 2006; Abioye, 2007; Nwosu & Udo-Anyanwu, 2015).

Contamination becomes hazardous when microbes form biofilms or release toxic metabolites such as mycotoxins, which persist on surfaces and spread through poor hygiene, dust accumulation, and improper handling (Miller, 2021; Penesyan et al., 2021). Libraries provide ideal conditions for such persistence, and common isolates including *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are known to cause both physical deterioration (brittleness, foxing) and chemical degradation (acidification) of collections (Zyska, 1997; Arai, 2000). Because microbial damage often progresses unnoticed until deterioration is severe and irreversible, preventive conservation is more effective than remedial measures (Tom et al., 2020). The high bioreceptivity of cellulose-rich paper further explains its susceptibility to fungal and bacterial attack (Hol et al., 2019).

Empirical studies highlight the scale of the problem bacterial concentrations ranging from 73–673 CFU/m³ and fungal loads reaching 893 CFU/m³ have been recorded in Nigerian university libraries, levels comparable to those reported in European studies (Gorny et al., 2005; Karbowska-Berent et al., 2011). Yet, Nigeria's environmental regulations still lack defined microbial thresholds for indoor air, leaving libraries unprotected (Nigeria Environmental Regulations, 2021). Tackling this challenge requires not only infrastructural investment and climate control measures but also strengthening the awareness, attitudes, and practices of librarians, whose daily decisions are central to contamination prevention and the sustainable preservation of resources.

Librarians' Awareness of Microbial Contamination

Awareness is foundational to effective microbial risk management. While librarians generally recognize that microbial contamination can affect library collections and user health, their understanding of specific risks such as the types of microorganisms involved, their health implications, and appropriate preventive measures remains limited, particularly in contexts where training and infrastructural support are inadequate (Sequiera et al., 2024). Rafaei et al. (2017) found that while librarians recognized books as vectors for pathogens, many were unaware of specific microorganisms such as *Enterobacter* spp. or coagulase-negative *Staphylococcus*, which pose significant health risks to vulnerable individuals. Kumar et al. (2021) similarly documented harmful fungal contaminants like *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*, which are linked to respiratory illnesses. Jung et al. (2019) highlighted the presence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria on children's library books, reinforcing the need for microbial literacy. Studies by Kalwasińska et al. (2012) demonstrated that dampness, poor airflow, and elevated humidity foster microbial proliferation in library environments. However, research in Nigeria highlights broader gaps in librarians' awareness of environmental preservation risks, which may extend to microbial triggers (Iwhiwhu, 2022). Loukou et al. (2024) further emphasized the critical importance of maintaining indoor humidity below 60% to inhibit fungal growth, although such standards are rarely implemented due to infrastructural limitations.

Although librarians may sometimes seem passive, this attitude often reflects how microbial risks are presented in scholarship as broader environmental or institutional concerns rather than matters of individual responsibility (El Jaddaoui et al., 2023). However, Landry et al. (2018) showed that targeted interventions, such as workshops and practical training, significantly strengthen librarians' preservation skills, particularly in detecting mold and managing microclimatic conditions.

Librarians' Attitudes to Microbial Contamination

Librarians' attitudes toward microbial contamination are shaped both by individual awareness and by the institutional culture in which they work. Bosco et al. (2020) observed that librarians with microbiological training are more likely to perceive contamination as a serious threat and to adopt preventive measures. In a similar vein, Foy (2024) reported that heightened awareness of health risks frequently motivates librarians to incorporate preventive strategies into their professional practice. This link between awareness and action resonates with broader findings in health literacy research, where Barr-Walker (2016) demonstrated that health information-seeking behaviors can be positively influenced through structured interventions such as workshops facilitated by health sciences librarians. Collectively, these studies emphasize the dual value of awareness: safeguarding both staff and collections while also empowering patrons to make more informed health decisions.

Yet, awareness alone does not guarantee consistent engagement. El Jaddaoui et al. (2023) highlighted that the absence of institutional support whether in the form of funding, tools, or policy frameworks frequently results in inaction, even among librarians who recognize mold contamination risks. Johnson and Oguntoye (2024) similarly showed that institutional support plays a decisive role in shaping preservation and conservation practices in Nigerian university

libraries. Their study revealed that where funding, policy, and training were adequate, librarians demonstrated more consistent and effective preservation practices, whereas inadequate support led to lapses and neglect. Isibor and Mamudu (2017) echoed these concerns, noting that preventive measures are often inconsistently applied due to resource constraints, insufficient staff capacity, and the tendency to shift responsibility for contamination control onto custodial staff rather than positioning it as a professional duty of librarians.

Taken together, these findings suggest that passivity toward microbial contamination is not simply a matter of indifference but often reflects systemic barriers rooted in institutional and resource-related factors. When contrasted with evidence showing that awareness of health risks can stimulate proactive engagement (Foy, 2024), a spectrum of librarian attitudes becomes visible ranging from passivity shaped by structural limitations to active participation fostered by health literacy and preventive responsibility. Recognizing this spectrum is essential for developing sustainable strategies that integrate both preservation priorities and occupational health responsibilities within library environments.

Librarians' Practices to Contamination Prevention

The management of microbial risks in libraries is fundamentally shaped by institutional practices, staff capacity, and environmental conditions (Bosco et al., 2020). Cobrado et al. (2017) highlight that high-contact surfaces across various settings harbour diverse microbial communities, including bacteria, yeasts, and viruses, particularly in the absence of systematic cleaning. In libraries, high touch zones such as circulation desks and shelving areas are consistently identified as hotspots for microbial accumulation, these areas are frequently exposed to human contact and repeated handling of materials, rendering them potential reservoirs for contamination.

This risk extends beyond surfaces to the materials themselves. Stephens et al. (2019) demonstrated that fomites objects repeatedly handled by multiple individuals play a critical role in microbial exchange. Books, documents, and other shared resources can retain viable microorganisms over prolonged periods, facilitating indirect transmission between patrons and staff. Rafiei et al. (2017) empirically reinforced this concern by revealing that a significant proportion of printed resources in libraries of Al-Zahra Hospital and the Faculty of Science at Isfahan University were contaminated with various bacterial species, including multidrug-resistant strains. These findings highlight that library materials are not inert but active fomites, capable of sustaining and transferring microorganisms with potential health implications.

Despite such evidence, formal sanitization protocols for circulating materials are rare in library practice, creating a significant gap in contamination control (Mamatha, 2022). This gap reflects broader institutional challenges, as the capacity to address microbial risks is influenced not only by awareness but also by policy, resource allocation, and infrastructure. Johnson and Oguntoye (2024) and Isibor and Mamudu (2017) emphasized that disparities in training, policy frameworks, and institutional support strongly determine whether preventive measures are implemented. Effective contamination management in libraries therefore requires integrated interventions that combine standardized cleaning protocols, particularly for high-touch surfaces and circulating materials, with sustained institutional commitment and adequate resources.

Environmental Conditions Influencing Microbial Contamination in Library Environments

The problem of microbial contamination in libraries arises from a dynamic interaction between abiotic (environmental) and biotic (biological) factors, each of which contributes to the persistence of microorganisms and the deterioration of collection materials (Gonzalez & Aranda, 2023). Among abiotic determinants, fluctuations in temperature, relative humidity, moisture accumulation, dust, air pollutants, and poor ventilation play a central role in microbial proliferation. Evidence from damp building studies demonstrates that such environments consistently harbour diverse fungal species that thrive in humid indoor conditions, highlighting humidity and moisture as critical drivers of fungal colonization and biodeterioration (Loukou, Jensen, Rohde, & Andersen, 2024). High temperatures combined with elevated humidity accelerate fungal and bacterial growth, with mesophilic fungi preferring temperatures between 20–25 °C, while some *Aspergillus* species can tolerate temperatures as high as 57 °C. Relative humidity above 60% provides favourable conditions for mold development and paper deterioration, whereas excessively low humidity renders paper brittle and weakens structural fibers. This dual risk of microbial degradation and desiccation-induced damage is well illustrated by Zhang, Wang, and Guo (2025), who showed that relative humidity fluctuations accelerate the chemical aging of palm leaf manuscripts by degrading cellulose, lignin, and hemicellulose. Such abiotic stressors not only compromise the mechanical and chemical integrity of materials through staining, smudging, and fiber breakdown but also increase the survival and dispersal of microbial bioaerosols, thereby amplifying contamination risks (Kakde, 2015).

Biotic factors further compound these vulnerabilities. Fungi, bacteria, insects, rodents, and human activity all interact with environmental stressors to sustain contamination. Dust and particulate matter act as efficient carriers of spores and bacteria, while poor cleaning regimes and overcrowded usage patterns heighten microbial loads in shared environments. Studies have reported that indoor bacterial concentrations in educational facilities correlate strongly with human occupancy and cleaning frequency, underscoring the contribution of everyday activities to microbial burden (Andualem et al., 2019). Humans contribute to contamination through skin shedding, coughing, and sneezing, while rodents and insects introduce droppings and fragments that serve as nutrient sources for microbial growth (Hayleeyesus & Manaye, 2014). Furthermore, poorly designed or inadequately maintained HVAC systems, particularly when coupled with high humidity, can intensify microbial proliferation and compromise overall air quality (Watanabe et al., 2022).

Environmental control emerges as a particularly critical yet often neglected aspect of contamination management. Parameters such as airflow, temperature, humidity, and ventilation are vital in reducing microbial loads, but technical and financial limitations frequently undermine effective implementation. Branco et al. (2024), in their review of indoor air quality in educational settings, emphasized that inadequate management of these environmental parameters promotes microbial persistence and contributes to respiratory and other health-related risks. These findings are highly relevant to library environments, where inadequate control of microclimatic conditions creates ideal niches for common microbial contaminants such as *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Cladosporium*, *Bacillus*, and *Staphylococcus*. These organisms flourish in humid, dusty, and poorly ventilated storage conditions, thereby jeopardizing both the preservation of collections and the health of library users and staff.

Ultimately, the degree to which these abiotic and biotic factors are mitigated depends not only on environmental and biological conditions but also on librarians' awareness, institutional policies, and the consistency of preservation practices. A holistic contamination management strategy must therefore integrate environmental monitoring, preventive cleaning, and stakeholder awareness to safeguard both cultural resources and indoor air quality.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to generate both statistical and contextual insights into microbial contamination management in federal university libraries. A descriptive survey design, complemented by observational and interview techniques, was adopted to enable triangulation of findings. This integration of quantitative and qualitative strands ensured methodological rigor by cross-verifying reported practices with direct observations and professional perspectives.

The study population comprised 634 library staff across six federal university libraries. From this population, a proportionate stratified random sampling technique was applied to ensure equitable representation of staff strength in each library. Using Yamane's (1967) formula at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, a total sample size of 239 respondents was determined. The distribution of the sample size by institution is presented in Table 1.

The quantitative component of the study involved a structured questionnaire designed to capture data on awareness, attitudes, and preventive practices regarding microbial contamination of print resources. Content validity was established through expert review by library and microbiology specialists, while a pilot test confirmed internal consistency with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82.

The qualitative strand comprised direct observations and semi-structured interviews. Observations focused on environmental conditions (e.g., ventilation, shelving, cleanliness), visible contamination of materials, and adherence to preservation protocols. Interviews with six (6) heads of the University libraries studied to further explored institutional policies, challenges, and support systems. Data integration was carried out at the interpretation stage, where findings from quantitative and qualitative sources were triangulated to provide a holistic picture of microbial contamination risks and management practices in Federal University libraries studied.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Distribution of Sample Size by Institution

SN	University Library	Number of Staff	Sample Size
1.	BUK Library	165	58
2.	UNILAG Library	156	39
3.	UNIPORT Library	46	10
4.	ATBU Library	129	49
5.	UNIABUJA Library	43	12

SN	University Library	Number of Staff	Sample Size
6.	UNN Library	95	29
7.	Total	634	239

Table 2: Awareness that Print Resources Can be Contaminated

SN	University	Yes (%)	No (%)
1.	BUK	51 (94.4%)	3 (5.6%)
2.	UniLag	33 (91.7%)	3 (8.3%)
3.	UniPort	7 (77.8%)	2 (22.2%)
4.	ATBU	42 (91.3%)	4 (8.7%)
5.	UniAbuja	8 (80.0%)	2 (20.0%)
6.	UNN	23 (88.5%)	3 (11.5%)

The findings reveals that awareness of microbial contamination of print resources is generally high across the six university libraries. BUK (94.4%), UniLag (91.7%), and ATBU (91.3%) reported the highest levels of awareness, while UniPort (77.8%) and UniAbuja (80.0%) had slightly lower figures, indicating possible gaps in staff training or exposure. Despite minor variations, the results suggest that most library personnel understand the risk of contamination, though some institutions may benefit from enhanced awareness initiatives.

Table 3: Librarians' Experiences That Built Awareness of Microbial Contamination

SN	Awareness Indicator	BUK	UNILAG	UNIPOINT	ATBU	UNIABUJA	UNN
1.	Reading books/articles on contamination	94	89	78	91	80	85
2.	Collaborating with preservation specialists	88	84	67	86	70	80
3.	Participation in conferences/workshops	89	85	67	83	70	81
4.	Exploring online resources/guidelines	91	86	78	85	70	83
5.	Hands-on experience in projects	87	82	67	83	68	79
6.	Networking with fellow librarians	88	84	70	84	72	80
7.	Encountering contaminated resources	89	86	78	85	75	82
8.	Taught about contamination in school	90	82	75	88	78	81
9.	Conducted research on contamination	86	80	65	83	68	79

The findings shows that librarians in BUK, ATBU, and UniLag consistently reported higher levels of exposure to learning and training on microbial contamination. These institutions show strong engagement in both theoretical and hands-on experiences, such as reading academic materials, collaborating with professionals, attending conferences, and engaging in practical projects. On the

other hand, UniPort and UniAbuja reported comparatively lower levels of awareness-building experiences. For instance, only 65–70% of UniPort librarians indicated involvement in research or conferences, and just 68–70% in UniAbuja reported collaboration or use of online resources. This gap reflects weaker institutional and professional development support in those libraries.

Table 4: Librarians’ Attitudes toward Microbial Contamination

SN	Attitudinal Statement (% Agreed)	BUK	UniLag	UniPort	ATBU	UniAbuja	UNN
1.	I consider microbial contamination a serious issue	94	92	78	91	80	88
2.	Importance of proactive measures	91	91	78	90	75	87
3.	Actively seek preventive information	89	83	67	81	70	79
4.	Willingness to collaborate	90	84	67	86	75	82
5.	Concern for personal health	91	86	70	89	75	85

The finding shows a high level of concern and awareness about microbial contamination among librarians in all six institutions, but with varying degrees of intensity. BUK and ATBU libraries consistently scored the highest across all indicators, reflecting a deep understanding of the health risks posed by microbial contamination and a proactive stance toward managing it. As 94% of BUK staff and 91% of ATBU staff consider microbial contamination a serious issue. Similarly, over 89% of librarians in both institutions are concerned about their health and actively seek preventive information. UniLag also reflects strong attitudes, with over 90% of respondents believing in proactive measures and acknowledging the seriousness of the issue. In contrast, UniPort and UniAbuja show lower levels of concern and engagement with only 67–70% of UniPort librarians expressed willingness to collaborate or seek preventive information. UniAbuja's figures suggest moderate concern (75–80%), but they trail behind in proactive behavior. These findings highlight the need for targeted awareness and training programs in institutions with weaker attitudes, especially to raise concern about health risks and promote collaborative mitigation efforts.

Table 5: Preventive Practices among Librarians

SN	Preventive Practice (% Yes)	BUK	UniLag	UniPort	ATBU	UniAbuja	UNN
1.	Handwashing before/after handling materials	89	85	70	83	65	79
2.	Use of protective gear (gloves, masks)	72	68	44	69	50	64
3.	Adherence to material care guidelines	84	79	60	80	58	72
4.	Educating users on handling	80	75	55	76	60	68
5.	Ensuring cleaning/disinfection protocols	86	78	67	80	60	74

The findings reveal significant variations in preventive practices among the libraries studied. BUK, UniLag, and ATBU demonstrate the highest adherence to good hygiene and contamination

prevention behaviors. These libraries recorded over 85% compliance with handwashing and disinfection protocols. Strong observance of library material handling guidelines (79–84%). Robust involvement in user education and protective practices. While UNN shows moderate compliance across all preventive measures, with slightly lower figures in user education (68%) and protective gear use (64%). UniPort and UniAbuja, on the other hand, show the weakest engagement as only 44–50% of staff in these libraries use protective gear when handling potentially contaminated materials. Hand hygiene and adherence to handling guidelines are also lower than in other libraries. User education on proper handling practices is underemphasized (55–60%). These findings highlight the critical importance of institutional support, training, and policy enforcement. While personal attitudes toward contamination may be strong, preventive practices can only be sustained through consistent guidance, infrastructure, and awareness programs.

Table 8: Observed Environmental Conditions in Libraries

SN	Condition Observed	BUK	UniLag	UniPort	ATBU	UniAbuja	UNN
1.	Adequate ventilation	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Partial
2.	Relative humidity control (40–60%)	Partial	Partial	No	Yes	No	Partial
3.	Visible mold/dust on shelves	No	Partial	Yes	Partial	Yes	Partial
4.	Proper shelving (airflow between stacks)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Partial
5.	Regular cleaning observed	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes

The environmental observations show better conditions in BUK, ATBU, and UniLag. UniPort and UniAbuja showed poor ventilation, visible mold, and lack of cleaning, suggesting higher susceptibility to microbial contamination.

Institutional Perspectives from Interviews

Semi-structured interviews with library heads highlighted both recognition of microbial risks and institutional gaps in addressing them. Across the six libraries, participants agreed contamination was a concern, yet levels of preparedness differed.

Policies and Frameworks. Participants from BUK (P1) and ATBU (P3) noted the existence of informal guidelines and periodic sensitization, though inconsistently applied. By contrast, UniPort (P4) and UniAbuja (P6) lacked formal policies, leaving preservation efforts to individual initiative.

Funding Limitations. Resource constraints were a recurring theme. All participants (P1 to P6) linked poor contamination control to inadequate budgets, limiting supplies such as gloves, disinfectants, and ventilation maintenance. P2 emphasized that preservation funds were often deprioritized in favor of other needs.

Training Gaps. Most participants (P1, P3, P4, and P6) identified limited staff training as a challenge, with only a few librarians exposed to workshops on microbial management. UniLag

(P2) and UNN (P5) occasionally accessed external seminars, but these were irregular and insufficient for sustained expertise.

Environmental Monitoring. Monitoring of humidity, temperature, and air quality was generally weak. Most participants admitted checks were rare, with BUK (P1) as the only case reporting limited monitoring tools.

Awareness versus Structures. While librarians displayed personal commitment and awareness, institutional systems policies, funding, training, and monitoring were inadequate. This imbalance underscores the need for stronger administrative commitment and structured preservation programs.

In conclusion, the findings reveal a fragmented institutional response: microbial risks are recognized, but systemic weaknesses hinder effective control. Strengthening policies, funding, and staff capacity is essential for sustainable preservation.

DISCUSSION

This study investigated librarians' awareness, attitudes, and practices regarding microbial contamination across six federal university libraries in Nigeria, while also assessing environmental conditions and institutional frameworks. By triangulating quantitative survey data, qualitative interviews, and direct observations, the research provides a multidimensional understanding of microbial risk management in library environments.

Awareness of Microbial Contamination

Survey findings indicated moderate to high awareness among librarians, with BUK and ATBU staff demonstrating the strongest levels. This resonates with Hayleeyesus and Manaye (2014) who reported that awareness of health risks often motivates preventive behaviors in indoor environments. Observational evidence supported these results, as libraries with more knowledgeable staff showed relatively better handling practices and cleaner shelving. Yet, interviews revealed gaps in institutional support, with heads of the libraries acknowledging that despite staff awareness, systematic training and policy backing remained inadequate. This echoes Gonzalez and Aranda (2023), who stressed that awareness without enabling conditions rarely translates into sustained preventive action.

Attitudes towards Microbial Risks

Survey responses highlighted generally positive attitudes, with librarians perceiving microbial contamination as both a preservation and health hazard. This aligns with El Jaddaoui et al. (2020), who noted that staff recognition of contamination risks fosters responsibility in preservation roles. However, observational data revealed inconsistencies between attitudes and actual practices, as routine cleaning and environmental monitoring were often neglected. Watanabe et al. (2022) argued that poorly maintained HVAC systems and environmental controls undermine even the most proactive attitudes an observation confirmed in this study, where librarians expressed

willingness but lacked infrastructural support. Interviews reinforced this disconnect, showing that attitudinal commitment was constrained by financial and administrative limitations.

Preventive Practices of Librarians

Survey results showed reliance on basic cleaning, dusting, and occasional fumigation, with minimal adoption of structured preservation protocols. This corroborates Kakde (2015), who emphasized that poor dust control significantly contributes to microbial spread in libraries. Observations confirmed dust accumulation, overcrowded shelves, and irregular disinfection across most libraries, echoing Branco et al. (2024), who reported that neglected indoor air quality directly increases microbial persistence. Interviews revealed that preventive practices were less informed by best practices and more dictated by limited resources and institutional neglect. These findings mirror Andualem et al. (2019), who demonstrated that inadequate cleaning regimes and overcrowding exacerbate microbial risks in public institutions.

Environmental Risk Factors

Observational data underscored environmental vulnerabilities such as poor ventilation, high humidity, and dust accumulation conditions conducive to fungal proliferation. Loukou et al. (2024) similarly reported that damp indoor environments consistently harbor diverse fungal species, underscoring humidity as a key determinant of contamination. In this study, RH levels above 60% in some libraries suggested risks of mold growth and paper deterioration, consistent with Zhang et al. (2025), who demonstrated that fluctuations in relative humidity accelerate the aging of cellulose, lignin, and hemicellulose in manuscripts. Libraries with poor air circulation and inadequate cleaning, particularly UniAbuja and UniPort, were most affected. Interviews with heads of the libraries attributed these risks to infrastructural decay and insufficient maintenance budgets, reflecting Hayleeyesus and Manaye's (2014) findings on the link between environmental neglect and microbial colonization.

Institutional and Policy Perspectives

Interview data revealed systemic weaknesses in institutional responses, including lack of clear preservation policies, inadequate funding, and limited staff training. These findings align with Branco et al. (2024), who emphasized that poor environmental management fosters microbial persistence and increases health risks in educational facilities. Survey and observation evidence corroborated these weaknesses, as preventive practices remained inconsistent and dependent on individual initiative rather than policy frameworks. As Gonzalez and Aranda (2023) highlighted, effective contamination control requires both environmental management and institutional accountability two areas where the libraries studied fell short.

Integrative Reflection

By triangulating surveys, observations, and interviews, this study demonstrates that microbial contamination in Nigerian university libraries is not primarily a matter of staff ignorance but is deeply rooted in structural and institutional deficiencies. The convergence of evidence shows that while librarians are aware of risks and generally maintain positive attitudes, their ability to

implement preventive practices is undermined by environmental challenges, resource scarcity, and weak policy frameworks. Divergences between self-reported practices and observational evidence emphasize the need for robust environmental monitoring, enforceable institutional policies, and regular capacity-building for staff. These findings are consistent with broader studies that highlights the complex interplay of biotic and abiotic factors in microbial persistence (Gonzalez & Aranda, 2023; Loukou et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025).

CONCLUSION

This study examined librarians' awareness, attitudes, practices, and environmental conditions influencing microbial contamination in six federal university libraries in Nigeria through a triangulated design of surveys, observations, and interviews. Findings revealed that while librarians demonstrated moderate to high awareness and generally positive attitudes toward microbial risks, preventive practices were inconsistent and often limited to basic cleaning and occasional fumigation. Observations highlighted significant environmental vulnerabilities, including poor ventilation, dust accumulation, and high humidity, while interviews with heads of the libraries studied exposed systemic challenges such as weak policy frameworks, insufficient funding, and inadequate staff training.

Conclusively, the results demonstrate that microbial contamination in university libraries is less a consequence of ignorance than of structural and institutional shortcomings. Addressing these challenges requires coordinated interventions that integrate environmental monitoring, consistent preservation practices, and strong institutional support systems. Strengthening these dimensions will not only safeguard library collections from biodeterioration but also protect the health of users and staff, ensuring that libraries remain safe and sustainable learning environments.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study highlight several gaps that require urgent scholarly and practical attention. First, the limited awareness of microbial contamination among librarians indicates the need for structured capacity-building. Awareness should not only be raised through ad-hoc workshops but institutionalized through continuous professional development programs, in-service training, and integration of microbial risk management modules into library and information science curricula. As Kakde (2015) argue, consistent exposure to preservation and contamination management knowledge fosters more proactive staff engagement in risk mitigation.

Second, the absence of formal preservation and contamination control policies across many of the libraries studied highlights the importance of institutionalizing clear guidelines. University libraries should develop written policies that articulate routine cleaning, safe disinfection protocols, pest management, and handling procedures for print materials. These policies should be disseminated to all staff and embedded in daily practice, with periodic reviews to accommodate emerging risks and scientific developments (Hayleeyesus & Manaye, 2014).

Third, the study revealed deficiencies in preventive practices, which require systematic intervention. Disinfection of library environments and contaminated materials should be regularized using scientifically tested disinfectants at recommended concentrations, while staff

should be provided with appropriate personal protective equipment. Furthermore, integrated pest and rodent control programs should be adopted as part of preventive measures, thereby addressing multiple sources of contamination simultaneously (Desoky, 2018).

Fourth, poor environmental conditions including inadequate ventilation, uncontrolled humidity, and poor shelving arrangements were found to significantly contribute to microbial proliferation. Universities should therefore prioritize infrastructural improvements such as functional HVAC systems, dehumidifiers, and proper shelving layouts to minimize dampness and crowding of materials. Equally important is the establishment of periodic monitoring of indoor air parameters, including temperature and relative humidity, with results recorded and used to inform preservation interventions (Branco et al., 2024).

The persistence of these problems reflects broader systemic challenges, including underfunding and weak regulatory frameworks. National policy actors such as the National Universities Commission (NUC) and the Nigerian Library Association (NLA) should mandate microbial risk management as part of accreditation and library quality assurance standards. Funding agencies and university administrations must also prioritize resource allocation for preservation infrastructures, thereby enabling libraries to implement preventive and remedial measures effectively (El Jaddaoui et al., 2021). By adopting these scholarly and policy-oriented interventions, Nigerian university libraries can reduce microbial risks, safeguard valuable collections, and protect the health of users and staff.

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